

Yernur Rakhimov

Senior Researcher, Department of the History of Kazakhstan
National Museum of the Republic of Kazakhstan
Acting Associate Professor, International University of Astana, PhD
e-mail: yernur_rakhimov@mail.ru
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Ainur Akzhasarova

Head of the Department of the History of Kazakhstan
National Museum of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Master of History
e-mail: ainur_7@mail.ru

**THE LEGACY OF KANYSH IMANTAEVICH SATPAEV IN
THE MUSEUMS OF KAZAKHSTAN**

Annotation. The article is devoted to the 125th anniversary of the birth of the outstanding geologist, the first president of the Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR, the famous statesman and public figure Kanysh Imantaevich Satpayev. The purpose of the study: to study and popularize the life of Kanysh Satpayev on the basis of museum materials. Based on the museum collections of the Memorial Museum of Academician K.I. Satpayev at the Academy of Sciences of Kazakhstan in Almaty, the Bayanauli Memorial Museum of Academician K.I. Satpayev, the house Museum of K.I. In the village of Karsakpai, Ulytau region, the main stages of the life path and scientific activity of an outstanding geologist have been studied and determined. Based on the overview analysis of K. Satpayev's museum collections, the stages of the life path, scientific and political activities of the outstanding geologist scientist are reflected. The author identifies the actual problems of preserving, studying and popularizing scientific creativity and the material heritage of Kanysh Imantaevich.

Key words: Satpayev, Museum, geology, Karsakpai, Zhezkazgan, Academy of Sciences of Kazakhstan, collection, photographic documents, works, personal belongings.

Introduction. Exhibition activities in museums are one of the most important means of promoting historical and cultural heritage. A priority direction of the exhibition work of the National Museum of the Republic of Kazakhstan is the creation of exhibitions dedicated to the memory of outstanding personalities of Kazakhstan. On April 19, 2014, the National Museum of the Republic of Kazakhstan opened the exhibition «Pride of the Nation», dedicated to the 125th anniversary of the outstanding scientist-geologist K. Satpaev. The exhibition was organized from the collections of the memorial museum of Academician K.I. Satpaev, the Bayanaul Memorial Museum named after K.I. Satpaev, and the house-museum of K.I. Satpaev in the village of Karsakpay. The exhibition included photographic documents, personal belongings, and awards of the scientist.

Image 1. View of the exhibition dedicated to the 125th anniversary of K.I. Satpayev

Materials and methods of research. The article uses museum materials from the collections of the memorial museum of Academician K.I. Satpayev, the Bayanauli Memorial Museum named after K.I. Satpayev, the house museum of K.I. Satpayev in the village of Karsakpai, publications. The method of structural analysis of museum collections of the memorial museum of academician K.I. Satpayev, the Bayanauli Memorial Museum named after K.I. Satpayev, the house museum of K.I. Satpayev in the village of Karsakpai was used; classification of collections and exhibits of the museum.

Discussion. Medeu Sarsek was one of the first to write about the academician's life and scientific path in the book "Satpayev", published in 1980 in Moscow. In 1963, on the advice of A. Margulan, he began studying the personality of K. Satpayev. When writing the book, there was a personal archive of Kanysh Imantaevich, stored at the Geological Institute, funds of archives and museums, memoirs of colleagues and fellow countrymen. In 1988-2010, the book on the biography of K. Satpayev was supplemented with new data and re-published nine times in Kazakh and Russian: "Kazaktyn Kanyshy" [1], "Satbayev planetasy" [2], "Kanysh aga" [3], "Satbayev" [4]. The political, social and scientific activities of K. Satpayev were highlighted in their writings by E.A. Buketov [5], K. Salykov [6], G.O. Batyrbekova [7]. Some aspects of

K. Satpayev's activity are covered in the publications of Sh. Shokin [8], A.Bragin [9], I.T.Lofovsky [10] and others.

Results. Kanysh Imantayevich Satpayev was born on April 12, 1899 in Pavlodar district of Semipalatinsk region. Kanysh studied first at the aul school, then at the two-grade Russian-Kazakh school in Pavlodar. In 1918, he graduated from the Seminary of Teachers in Semey, having passed the exams externally. Satpayev spent the years 1920-1921 in his native lands, where he returned to kumysotherapy. During this period, he was working on compiling a "Textbook on algebra for Kazakh schools in his native language." The manuscript of the textbook was discovered by M. Sarsekeev when he studied the personal archive of the academician. The manuscript consists of 1642 pages. In the preface of the textbook, the author points out that the difficult situation of Kazakh schools at the beginning of the twentieth century prompted the compilation of a textbook on algebra: the curriculum of schools, teacher training were unsatisfactory, there were not enough personnel and there were no textbooks in the Kazakh language [10, P. 49].

A reprinted version of the textbook is presented at the exhibition. A significant part of the exhibition consisted of photographs covering his childhood years in Bayanaul, student life at Tomsk Technological University. After graduating from the Tomsk Polytechnic Institute, the young specialist was sent to the Atbasar Non-ferrous Metals Trust by the head of the geological department, and the next section characterizes the beginning of his work - conducting exploration work in Karsakbai [2, p. 9]. The history of the development of copper deposits in Kazakhstan dates back to 1906. Atbasar Copper Mines JSC was established in London, which bought up the mines of Zhezkazgan. This company also bought out iron mines, lime quarries, and coal deposits in the Baikonur area.

In 1913, the British began construction of a copper smelter in the Karsakbai tract, the equipment and mechanisms necessary for the Zhezkazgan, Karsakbai, and Baikonur industries were delivered by narrow-gauge railway from the Zhosaly station.

The exhibition contains archival documents related to JSC "Atbasar copper Mines": correspondence with the company "Gerhard and Gay" on the supply of equipment for the Atbasar plant from 1914, a letter to the Steppe Governor-General from the Ministry of Internal Affairs on the merger of JSC "Spassky Copper Ores" and JSC "Atbasar Copper Mines", a message to Mr. District Engineer From the miner of the Spassky Copper Smelter K.E. Karno, a message about the strike of Kazakhs working at the mine furnaces of the Spassky plant on June 12, 1912, demanding an increase in wages. British entrepreneurs failed to complete the plant, but in its place in the Karsakpai-Asha tract on the banks of the Kumola River, the Soviet government opened a copper smelter.

So, in 1928, the first alloy of red copper was obtained in Karsakbai. Further expansion of production in Ulytau became possible after the establishment of copper ore reserves by geologist Kanysh Satbaev. Thanks to his geological research, the Zhezkazgan Mining and Metallurgical Combine was built in the 30s of the twentieth century. During the Second World War, a secret workshop No. 1 was opened at the Karsakpai plant, which produced 72-mm mine hulls. The order of January 15, 1942 on the establishment of a plan for the production of ammunition elements for the 1st quarter and January 1942 in the amount of 20 tons / piece, also the mine case is shown at the exhibition. Among the materials related to the period of his work in Karsakpai, there are copper samples, a badge-pass to the Atbastsvetmet plant, a manuscript by K.I. Satpayev "Power, technical standards and norms of equipment production at drilling operations of the Zhezkazgan Mining Complex for 1936", production characteristics for senior drilling foreman Tungyshpaev Murzabek, compiled by the head of the Geological Department.

The book "Bolshoy Zhezkazgan", published in Moscow in 1934, is of great value. The book "Bolshoy Zhezkazgan" is a transcript of the session of the USSR Academy of Sciences, where the issue of Bolshoy Zhezkazgan and the Greater Altai was specifically considered. This scientific meeting played a crucial role in the

development of the copper region. In 1941, Kanysh Imantaevich was appointed director of the Geological Institute, a year later he became the head of the Kazakh branch of the USSR Academy of Sciences. It is known that Kazakhstan made a significant contribution to the victory in the Great Patriotic War. Under the guidance of K. Satpayev, deposits of molybdenum, manganese, coal, iron, and lead have been discovered and developed. In December 1942, Kanysh Imantaevich wrote on the pages of the newspaper *Kazakhstanskaya Pravda* in a Letter to the Kazakhstani front-line soldiers that every 9 out of 10 bullets striking the fascists were cast from Kazakhstani lead. In 1942, the Zhezdinsky manganese mine was opened.

At the beginning of the war, the German army occupied Ukraine and the Caucasus, where the main manganese deposits in the Soviet Union were located. These deposits yielded more than 90 percent of the manganese ore used to create armored tank steel. On August 29, 1941, a meeting of the USSR Council of People's Commissars was held dedicated to the search for new manganese deposits. The People's Commissar of Ferrous Metallurgy is contacted by Kazakh geologist K. Satpayev said that in 1928, during geological exploration, he discovered manganese deposits in Zhezkazgan. Under his leadership, the exploration team conducts research in this area, sends preliminary calculations to the People's Commissariat of Ferrous Metallurgy. In the autumn of 1941, a commission from Moscow came to Zhezdy, which concluded that manganese was available in Zhezdy, but exploration work needed to be carried out, and the available stock was based on insufficient material."

The exhibition contains an official letter from Kanysh Satpayev addressed to I.I. Malyshev, Head of the Committee on Geology at the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR. In this letter, K. Satpayev points out in detail and in detail his disagreement with the decision of the TKZ on the development of the Zhezdinsky and other manganese ore deposits on the territory of Zhezkazgan: "...The tense situation with manganese dictated the need for the early development of the Zhezdinsky and other manganese deposits in the Zhezkazgan district, located near the road line in an

industrially populated area and possessing significant reserves of high-grade oxidized manganese ores." [13, revenue book No. 13105].

The content of the letter characterizes his struggle to open a nest. The Zhezdinsky deposit was discovered in a few months and provided manganese ore to the entire defense industry of the USSR. The complex of geological instruments of Kanysh Imantaevich is of interest. These are a helmet, a geological hammer, a mountain compass, a scale ruler, a magnifying glass, a stereoscope, a planimeter, a tape measure, a microscope, a pen, manuscripts and documents, a writing instrument, etc. The collection of minerals collected by Kanysh Imantaevich has been preserved. One part of the exposition consists of written sources presented by documents of his political and scientific activities.

In June 1946, Satpayev was elected the first president of the Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR, and then an academician of the USSR Academy of Sciences. In the same year, he was elected a deputy of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR. This is evidenced by the following documents: certificate of the President of the Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR, Honored Scientist of the Kazakh SSR, membership cards, certificate of a member of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Kazakhstan, certificate of a deputy of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, mandates, etc. A set of photographs reflecting his activities at that time is presented in chronological order: with scientists, geologists, party leaders, delegates of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR. In photographs taken during a business trip as part of the deputies of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR to London in 1947, the academician is depicted in a hat and coat.

Image 2. K.I. Satpayev's coat on exhibition at the National Museum.

Currently, the coat is kept in the museum. In 1966, to the Memorial Museum of Academician K. In Bayanaul, the scientist's family handed over his personal belongings in the amount of 44 units. The museum has preserved a list of transferred items. Number 12 indicates a drape coat that Kanysh Imantaevich wore in the late 1940s - early 1950s. The coat is brown, has a straight cut, double-breasted, turn-down collar with lapels. Internal side pockets [12, Act No. 2 of 11/24/1966, receipt book No. 13]. The next museum item is a rectangular travel suitcase with a metal clasp in the form of a keyhole. The handle is made of leather, fastened on both sides with metal brackets. Inside, the suitcase was covered with a cotton cloth (Karsakpai).

According to Meiz's daughter, Kanysh Imantaevich used a suitcase during a trip to London. A penknife presented to an academician in London in 1947 is of interest. The inscription "Satpayev" is engraved on the handle of the knife. The museum item is kept in the Memorial Museum of Academician K.I. Satpayev in Almaty. The list of 44 items transferred to the museum includes a collection of souvenirs and gifts presented to the 50th anniversary of Kanysh Imantaevich from colleagues, friends and relatives. This is the painting "Surroundings of Almaty" from the Union of Artists of Kazakhstan, the periodic table on metal from the Institute of Chemistry of the Academy

of Sciences of Kazakhstan and others. The academician's dombra is of great value – a gift from Shamshiyaban's daughter. At the request of Kanysh Imantaevich, dombra was kept in his daughter's house. He played it when he came to visit her. It is known that Kanysh Imantaevich loved to play the dombra: photographs have been preserved depicting him with a dombra in his hands. It is also known that the collector of folklore A. Zataevich managed to record 25 Kazakh folk songs performed by Kanysh Imantaevich.

Image 3. K.I. Satpayev's dombra.

The saddle, belt, and cane belonging to K. Satpayev are unique items. In 2012, a relative of T. Shashenov donated to the Bayanaul Museum a saddle used by the young Kanysh. The saddle is made of birch, the front part is inlaid with silver and colored stones. The cane was preserved and transferred to the museum by a relative of the scientist, an honorary teacher from Bayanaul G. Abylkhairova in 2010. The wooden cane is decorated with silver and carvings. Currently, the saddle and cane are stored in the Memorial Museum of Academician K.I. Satpayev in Bayanaul under No. 00763 and No. 00032 [12].

Among the scientist's personal belongings are glasses in a case, a pen, a pencil,

a hat and gloves, a suit, a hat, a purse, a snuffbox, a toothbrush, an electric razor, a kесе, a silver spoon with the initials of the scientist, etc. Among the awards are the Order of Lenin, which the geologist was awarded four times: in 1940 for the discovery of the Zhezkazgan deposit, in 1945 for the mobilization of rear resources, in 1957 for the mobilization of the Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR for the development of virgin and fallow lands, in 1963 for the development of geological science of Kazakhstan and mineral exploration. The documentary material of K. Satpayev: the laureate of the Lenin Prize, the laureate of the USSR State Prize is exhibited.

Conclusion. The museum collection of Kanysh Imantaevich Satpayev, who made a huge contribution to the development of Russian science, is of cultural value. The exhibition "Uly maktanyshy" at the National Museum of Kazakhstan was visited by a large number of residents and guests of the capital. Within the framework of the Uly Maktanyshy exhibition, the staff of the Museum Pedagogy department held a lecture on the Day of Science of Kazakhstan and the 125th anniversary of K. Satpayev for students of secondary school No. 49. On April 19, 2024, the National Museum also hosted an international scientific and practical conference dedicated to the anniversary of Academician K. Satpayev.

Leading foreign and Kazakhstani scientists made presentations – Deputy Director of the Institute of State History Ayagan Burkitbai Gelmanovich ("The history of repression of Academician K.I. Satpayev in 1940-1950"), Director of the Institute of Geology, Earthquake-resistant Construction and Seismology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tajikistan Aminzoda Pulod ("Contribution of K.I. Satpayev to the economic development of Kazakhstan and Tajikistan), Professor of the Geology Department of the Engineering School of Natural Resources of Tomsk Polytechnic University Yazikov Egor Grigoryevich ("Kanysh Imantaevich Satpayev – from a graduate of the Polytechnic to an academician"), leading researcher at the Institute of Geology, Earthquake-resistant Construction and Seismology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tajikistan Mavloni S.R. ("K.I. Satpayev is an

outstanding scientist and the organizer of Central Asian science"), Professor at the L.N. Eurasian National University. Gumilyova Darkenov Kurmangali Gazezovich ("K.Sapayev: the formation of personality") and others. At the conference, scientists discussed Kanysh Imantaevich's contribution to the formation and development of science in Kazakhstan, presented new archival materials about the academic's scientific activities.

The study of museum collections presented at the exhibition "Ult maktanyshy" ("Pride of the Nation") from the funds of the Memorial Museum of Academician K.I. Satpayev at the Academy of Sciences of Kazakhstan, the Memorial Museum of Academician K.I. Satpayev in Bayanaul, the house museum of K.I. Satpayev in the village of Karsakpai, Ulytau region showed that photographic documents, manuscripts, works, personal things are an important source in popularizing the life of a scientist.

Image 4. At the conference dedicated to the 100th anniversary of K.I. Satpayev at the National Museum of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

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НАСЛЕДИЕ КАНЫША ИМАНТАЕВИЧА САТПАЕВА В МУЗЕЯХ КАЗАХСТАНА

Аннотация. Статья посвящена 125-летию со дня рождения выдающегося учёного-геолога, первого президента Академии наук Казахской ССР, известного государственного и общественного деятеля Каныша Имантаевича Сатпаева.

Цель: раскрытие жизнедеятельности К.И. Сатпаева на основе материалов мемориального музея ученого в Академии наук Казахстана (г. Алматы), музея К.И. Сатпаева в поселке Баянаул (Павлодарская область), а также мемориального музея в поселке Карсакпай (Улытауская область). На основе изучения коллекций данных музеев определены основные этапы жизни и научной деятельности учёного-геолога, его научной и политической деятельности. Авторы обозначили актуальные вопросы сохранения, изучения и популяризации научного творчества и материального наследия Каньша Имантаевича Сатпаева.

Ключевые слова: Сатпаев, музеи, Баянаул, геология, Карсакпай, Жезказган, Академия наук РК, коллекция, фотографии, произведения, личные вещи.